

Equalizing equities

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A previous article [1] presented ways to reduce the dynamic range of historical data of stock market equities, attempting to minimize the impact of stock splits. Another approach is presented below, using Walmart (WMT) as an example.

The image below charts WMT stock price in the top tier, displayed on log-scale in the lower tier.

Log-rescaling has over-blown the area of the numerical past (up to year 2000), which now fills three times **more** vertical space (lower tier) in log-price, when in fact filling about five times **less** space in actual price (top tier); so the log scale has *emphasized* the past in favor of the present!

Is there another way? See below.

Above, the top tier has the historical WMT price data, the middle tier its 'equalized' version; the residual off a linear fit is at the bottom, including a zero-line in red. Some observations:

1. The equalized price history is now almost linear, with no timeline preference.
2. The residual has amplified large movements during 1986-1996, not obvious in the price data.
3. Local turbulence throughout suggests utility in trading strategies.
4. A stock **Score** is available as a percentage of positive residual: **Score = 46.576**

How was this done? The original idea was to find a measure of angular displacement of a data segment off the horizontal (see image below)

Thus (in degrees)

$$\theta = (180/\pi)\arctan(\text{range}/\text{block})$$

In the equalized display above, block=3 price-samples; output using block=10 is shown below.

Some qualitative differences are evident above - particularly after 2010 - when compared with the previous shorter-sample equalization; the Score, however, was similar: **Score = 49.509**. For good measure, results for a 30-day equalization are displayed next.

The Score this time was a bit higher: **Score = 54.422**. Interestingly, this Residual display shows the upward movement in price began near 2010, long before reflected in the historical data.

Unfortunately, no single data-sample horizon appeared best for equalization; however, options are at least available to explore numerical behavior, perhaps even to define strategies if greater price granularity is available.

Let's work the more recent WMT data, from 2020 onward; side-by-side below are results for 5 and 10 block equalizations.

Finally, results for estimated yearly scores for WMT (5-sample equalization) are plotted below; average overall Score was 49.924, not very different from previous estimates.

OCTAVE code.

```

% Equalizer
% dat is the stock historical data
clear ang,clear pic,clear res
len=length(dat);

blok=10; % Sampling rate
back=floor(len/blok);
tot=blok*back;

% This is the 'secret sauce'
pic=reshape(dat(1:tot),back,blok);

for j=1:back
ang(j)=(180/pi)*atan(range(pic(j,:))/blok);
end

% Linear fit & residual

clear val, clear res
t=1:1:back;
val=polyval(polyfit(t,ang,1),t); % poly fit
res=ang-val;

% Positive & Negative residual parts
pos=max(res,0);,neg=max(-res,0);

% Stock score
Score=100*sum(sign(pos))/back

```

[1] A. Cusmariu, 'Equity renormalization', <https://zenodo.org/records/15320335>, 2025